

varieties (results not presented). Few *O. glaberrima* varieties had the same reaction pattern.

These results suggest that numerous specific resistance genes are present in *O. glaberrima* some of them different from those found in *O. sativa*. Different combinations of these genes imply the diversity of reactions found.

The 32 resistant or intermediate varieties identified divide into two groups. TG10, BG155, BG162, BG178, YG12, YG15, YG247, YG304, and MG26 are resistant to all strains used. This means that these varieties have specific resistance genes, and that corresponding virulence genes are rare in the Ivory Coast pathogen population. The 23 varieties that scored 4 could carry a high level of general resistance. The genetic basis of that resistance should be studied. ■

Pest resistance – insects

Comparison of standard evaluation system and Oñate's method in assessing stalk-eyed fly resistance

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The stalk-eyed fly *Diopsis longicornis* Macquart is an indigenous dipterous rice stem borer found all over Africa. Infestation by the larva causes deadhearts.

We evaluated 27 rice genotypes against stalk-eyed fly during 1989 wet season—24 from Asia; one *O. sativa* (Koko) and one *O. glaberrima* from Africa; and standard susceptible check Suakoko 8. Adult flies collected in the field were released in a screenhouse sited in an irrigated ricefield at IITA.

Deadhearts were assessed by Oñate's method (normal practice in Africa) and *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES) 45 and 60 d after transplanting (DT).

No variety was highly resistant (0 damage). ARC10331, Parakulam, and

Assessing rice resistance to SEF, using two methods. Nigeria, 1989 WS.

Genotype	Deadhearts (%) ^a			
	Method 1		Method 2	
	45 DT (X ± S.E.)	60 DT (X ± S.E.)	45 DT (X ± S.E.)	60 DT (X ± S.E.)
ARC 5823	16 ± 3	21 ± 3	16 ± 3	22 ± 3
ARC 5912	19 ± 3	24 ± 5	18 ± 3	25 ± 5
ARC 5989	18 ± 2	20 ± 3	18 ± 2	21 ± 3
ARC 6157	6 ± 2	12 ± 2	6 ± 2	12 ± 2
ARC 6619	17 ± 2	20 ± 4	17 ± 3	20 ± 4
ARC 6632	22 ± 2	34 ± 3	20 ± 2	31 ± 4
ARC 7255	11 ± 4	19 ± 5	11 ± 4	19 ± 5
ARC 10331	8 ± 3	5 ± 2	8 ± 3	5 ± 2
ARC 10660	15 ± 3	16 ± 2	15 ± 3	17 ± 3
Balam	91 ± 3	14 ± 2	9 ± 3	14 ± 3
Bhumansan	16 ± 3	16 ± 3	16 ± 3	16 ± 3
BG 276-5	14 ± 2	21 ± 3	13 ± 2	22 ± 3
BG 380	13 ± 3	25 ± 4	14 ± 3	27 ± 4
Chekhalopoiortal	13 ± 4	10 ± 4	11 ± 3	10 ± 4
CR57-MR 1523	11 ± 2	10 ± 2	10 ± 2	10 ± 2
Kakatiya	11 ± 4	11 ± 3	10 ± 3	11 ± 3
Moirangphou	10 ± 2	16 ± 2	10 ± 2	16 ± 2
Parakulam	6 ± 3	10 ± 3	5 ± 3	10 ± 3
Phodum	15 ± 3	16 ± 3	14 ± 3	16 ± 3
Rajendradhan	10 ± 3	11 ± 3	9 ± 3	11 ± 3
T10	16 ± 1	13 ± 2	16 ± 1	13 ± 2
T1477	14 ± 4	12 ± 2	14 ± 4	11 ± 2
<i>O. sativa</i> (Koko)	19 ± 3	33 ± 4	19 ± 3	33 ± 4
<i>O. glaberrima</i>	5 ± 3	8 ± 3	5 ± 3	9 ± 3
Suraksha	16 ± 2	14 ± 3	16 ± 2	14 ± 2
Vikramarya	11 ± 2	17 ± 2	11 ± 2	17 ± 2
Suakoko 8 (susceptible check)	34 ± 5	32 ± 4	33 ± 5	30 ± 4

^a Av of 10 replications. DT = days after transplanting. ^bPercentage deadhearts computed by *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES) (1988). ^cPercentage deadhearts computed by Oñate (1965) method as:

$$X = P\bar{X}_{nz} 100$$

where

$$P = \frac{\text{number of affected hills}}{\text{number of hills in the plot (row)}}$$

$$\bar{X}_{nz} = \frac{\text{number of deadhearts}}{\text{number of tillers in the affected hills}}$$

O. glaberrima scored resistant (< 10% deadhearts) at 45 and 60 DT by both evaluation methods (see table). In all other varieties, more deadhearts were found at 60 DT than at 45 DT, probably because the flies were confined, and additional young tillers became susceptible as the plants

approached maximum tillering. Results of both evaluation methods were comparable at 45 and 60 DT. We recommend that screening be evaluated using SES. It is as precise as Oñate's method, and is easier and faster. Oñate's method is practical only when a few genotypes are screened. ■

Reactions of promising rice cultivars to gall midge (GM)

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GM *Orseolia oryzae* (Wood-Mason) is the most important pest of rice in

Vidarbha region, Maharashtra State. We screened 56 promising entries for resistance during 1987-89 wet seasons.

Entries were transplanted in 3-m-long rows spaced 20 cm apart. Total number of tillers and affected tillers (silvershoots) 50 d after transplanting were recorded on 10 hills selected randomly in each row. Ten entries were resistant (see table). ■

Reaction of promising rice entries to gall midge infestation in the field. 1987-89 wet seasons.

Average silvershoots (%)	Lines
0-5	CR404-48, CR407-19, CR401-7, CR401-6, Neela, CR404-3-2, CR95-181-2, SKL-99-15-5-25-5, Samalie, and Sarasa
5-10	Usha, SKL-6-1-23, Chinoor, SKL-11-33-3-9-2, and Sye-4-119-10-3-9-3
10-20	N22, Cauvery, Ratna, Sye-23-24, Sye-9-16-10, SKL-37-33-31-19, SKL-10-3, SKL-780-07-32-11-5, SKL-47-12, SKL-3-11, SKL-69-50-25-22, SKL-14-26-1-20-85-5, SKL-47-8, SKL-83-18-23-16-19, Pusa 33, Tuljapur 1, Ratnagiri 24, Tellahamsa, Patel 3, Sye-473-21-31-15-1-3-4, Sye-148-95, Sye-75, Sye-1-119-39-6-4-5, Sye-1-484-1-17, Sye-34-4-39, Sye-228-10-25-9-7-18, RP4-14, Pankaj, IR28, Jagannath, and CR407-6-2
20 or more	SKL-6, Sye-3-43-57, Sye-88-13-3-31, Sye-1-84-1-17, Sye-17-6-7-81-31-26-3, Sye-158-32-36-23, Sye-3-43-57, RTN 68-1, TN1, Jaya (check)

Pest resistance – other pests

Variations in termite susceptibility in rice varieties

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Upland ricefields are well suited to infestations by subterranean termites (family Termitidae) because they are not flooded. Damage due to termites is widespread in the upland rice areas of Chotanagpur, Bihar. Infestations are heavier in the red loam soils, especially during drought.

We have observed severe infestations at on-farm research sites in several villages. Traditional gora rices are perceptibly less damaged than high-yielding rices such as Kalinga III (2.5-50% reduction in plant population).

Preliminary investigations at CRURRS indicated differential reaction

to termite attack among upland varieties. Of 16 International Upland Rice Yield Nursery-Early cultures tested in replicated trials during 1989 wet season (WS), IR47686-4-5-B1 and IR47686-9-4 were highly susceptible to *Microtermes* sp. Damage was as high as 90%. Of test entries of the International Upland Rice Observational Nursery grown during 1989 WS, ITA257 was susceptible.

In 1990 WS, IR47686-4-5-B1, IR47686-9-4, ITA257, and several other promising upland rice genotypes were grown in a four-row observational nursery. Test plots were interchanged to partially eliminate infested plot interference. The test site was surrounded by field borders planted to perennial *Lantana* species on two sides and maize crop on the other two.

Infestation on the three entries was consistent with cumulative reduction in plant population at 50 d after sowing; it

ranged from 47% in ITA257 to 63% in IR47686-4-5-B1. Seedlings were more susceptible to termite attack than were germinating seeds. Reduction in plant population in the other varieties was less than 3%.

The selective damage to certain genotypes indicates varietal preference. This could be due to variation in rooting depth. Our preliminary observations indicate that genotypes such as Brown Gora that have relatively deeper root systems are less damaged than genotypes having horizontal root systems. It seems possible to breed for tolerance for termite infestation.

IR47686-4-5-B1 could be used as a susceptible check, but a cultivar exhibiting consistently low infestation under high termite pressure is needed for a resistant check. We are working on a mass screening technique to identify suitable donors of termite tolerance. ■

Integrated germplasm improvement – irrigated

Properties of two new rice varieties released in India

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Mandyavijaya and IR30864 were recently released for cultivation in Karnataka. We tested grain samples collected from the V.C. Farm, Mandya, for technological properties and consumer acceptability.

Mandyavijaya, derived from Sona and Mahsuri, is semitall (average plant height 97 cm), with 140- to 145-d duration and 7-7.5 t/ha yield potential. IR30864 is a selection from the cross 17-38/IR7801-1-2-1/IR46/Khao Lo with 135-140 d duration, and with 7.5-8 t/ha yield potential.

Both varieties largely satisfy the technological norms and cooking and eating qualities desirable under Indian conditions (see table). Husk is in the optimum 18-20% range, with 74% milling outturn. Milled rice is bright and translucent, free of chalkiness. Protein content averages

Technological properties of rice varieties Mandyavijaya and IR30864.

Quality attribute	Mandyavijaya	IR30864
Grain yield (t/ha)	7.5	7.5
Husk content (%)	20.1	18.4
Milled rice yield (%)	73.9	75.6
Length (mm)	5.7	6.85
Length/breadth ratio	2.85	3.19
Normalized grain weight (mg/cm) ^a	22.5	27.0
Protein (%)	7.8	7.1
Amylose (%)	30.4	29.0
Cooking time (min)	17	16
Cooked rice volume (ml/100g)	380	360
Texture	Soft	Soft
Consistency	Very fluffy	Fluffy
Appearance of milled rice	Bright, translucent	Bright, translucent
Overall	Highly acceptable	Highly acceptable

^aNormalized grain weight = $\frac{10 \times \text{kernel weight (mg)}}{\text{kernel length (cm)}}$

7.1% in IR30864 and 7.8% in Mandyavijaya. Both varieties have high amylose. Milled rice took an average 16-17 min to cook. Cooked rice was soft and fluffy.

Mandyavijaya gave more straw yield than its parents. IR30804 exhibited salt tolerance. ■